

"Jaunizolētu *Aeromonas* spp. inficējošu bakteriofāgu un to saimnieku mijiedarbības izpēte praktiskam pielietojumam"

Version 1

Description

Aeromonas ģints baktērijas ir multi-rezistenti, nozīmīgi zivju patogēni visā pasaulē, kuri negatīvi ietekmē arī Latvijas akvakultūru. Viena no alternatīvām šo baktēriju biokontrolei ir fāgu terapija. Šī pētījuma gaitā tiks padziļināti izpētīti un publicēti Latvijas akvakultūrai aktuālo *Aeromonas* spp. celmu inficējošo fāgu genomi un to fenotipiskās īpašības, kas būtiski paplašinās zināšanas par šo baktēriju vīrusiem, kā arī to mijiedarbību un kalpos par pamatu iedarbīgas zivju patogēnu biokontroles radīšanā un tālākā testēšanā. Pētījuma "otrajā daļā" tiks rastas atbildes uz fundamentāliem fāgu evolūcijas aspektiem, kas saistīti ar plaša saimniekspektra fāgu pielāgošanos dažādām saimniekbaktērijām.

Funder

Atveseļošanas fonda projekts

Grant

ANM doktorantūras grants

Researchers

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Organizations

LATVIJAS BIOMEDICINAS PETIJUMU UN STUDIJU CENTRS

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: "Jaunizolētu *Aeromonas* spp. inficējošu bakteriofāgu un to saimnieku mijiedarbības izpēte praktiskam pielietojumam"

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Aeromonas ģints baktērijas ir multi-rezistenti, nozīmīgi zivju patogēni visā pasaulē, kuri negatīvi ietekmē arī Latvijas akvakultūru. Viena no alternatīvām šo baktēriju biokontrolei ir fāgu terapija. Šī pētījuma gaitā tiks padziļināti izpētīti un publicēti Latvijas akvakultūrai aktuālo *Aeromonas* spp. celmu inficējošo fāgu genomi un to fenotipiskās īpašības, kas būtiski paplašinās zināšanas par šo baktēriju vīrusiem, kā arī to mijiedarbību un kalpos par pamatu iedarbīgas zivju patogēnu biokontroles radīšanā un tālākā testēšanā. Pētījuma "otrajā daļā" tiks rastas atbildes uz fundamentāliem fāgu evolūcijas aspektiem, kas saistīti ar plaša saimniekspektra fāgu pielāgošanos dažādām saimniekbaktērijām.

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Contact:

2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Atveseļošanas fonda projekts](#)

Grants: [ANM doktorantūras grants](#)

Project:

3. License

License: other-pd

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

LCS FARP

Description of genomic data and experimental wet lab datasets for "Jaunizolētu *Aeromonas* spp. inficējošu bakteriofāgu un to saimnieku mijiedarbības izpēte praktiskam pielietojumam" (ANM_K_DG_29).

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data generated and published will significantly enhance the phage library potentially usable for *Aeromonas* spp. biocontrol, the second part of the project involves in-depth analysis of a phage evolution in different bacteria species building the knowledge of virus adaptation and specialization to a single host.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Experimental data
- Textual data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- PNG
- XLS
- Others

FASTQ, GenBank Flat File

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

In this case there is no pre-existing data of importance that i could use

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other phage scientists and virologists in general, maybe even epidemiologists.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

Other

Each complete annotated bacteriophage genome will have a unique identifier called an "accession number" assigned by the time of release by the respective database. For example, based on the GenBank database standards (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/samplerecord/>): "The unique identifier for a sequence record. An accession number applies to the complete record and is usually a combination of a letter(s) and numbers, such as a single letter followed by five digits (e.g., U12345) or two letters followed by six digits (e.g., AF123456).

Some accessions might be longer, depending on the type of sequence record. Accession numbers do not change, even if information in the record is changed at the author's request. Sometimes, however, an original accession number might become secondary to a newer accession number, if the authors make a new submission that combines previous sequences, or if for some reason a new submission supercedes an earlier record." Similarly, Illumina and/or ONT read datasets uploaded publicly shall be accessioned through Sequencing Read Archive.

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

NCBI database metadata standards, e.g., BioSample

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/biosample>

There are International Nucleotide Sequence Database Collaboration standards, we will upload data through the National Centre Of Biotechnology Information services (e.g., Sequencing Read Archive requiring registration of BioSample, and GenBank).

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

The Taxonomy Database

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/taxonomy>

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.7 Other relevant remarks

The structure of the files and metadata shared will be uniform by the virtue of adherence to the Sequencing Read Archive upload forms and GenBank Flat File format standards, which are in compliance with the INSDC database terms.

GenBank Flat File format and INSDC database standards imply a seamless integration of all the Entrez terms corresponding to the standardized search fields of INSDC databases to files publicly released through these databases. E.g., see <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK49540/> and <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK3837/> for controlled vocabulary and query mapping descriptions.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

The contemporary publication standards for scientific articles containing bacteriophage genomics aspects warrant the necessity of the data being publicly accessible upon publication. This intrinsically implies that any embargo period will not be longer than the deadlines stated for the achievement of the key

performance indicators within the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

GenBank

GenBank is part of the International Nucleotide Sequence Database

Collaboration, which comprises the DNA DataBank of Japan (DDBJ), the European

Nucleotide Archive (ENA), and GenBank at NCBI. These three organizations

exchange data on a daily basis. Sharing data through GenBank (and,

consequently, other largest public biological sequence repositories by derivation)

ensures the widest possible reach of our data, as well as maximizes its impact on

the scientific community.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

GenBank Flat File format is a human-readable structured text-based format. This essentially means that the files can be accessed using any text editor (e.g.,

Notepad or Nano, among others). The availability of the comprehensive libraries

to work with GenBank files ensures the possibility of easily manipulating the data

in GenBank format programmatically. More specialized GUI software, both

commercial (e.g., Geneious, etc.) and open-source (e.g., UGENE, Artemis,

DNAMaster, etc.), exists for GenBank file manipulations and is largely a matter of

personal preference.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.2.7 Other relevant remarks

For this project the plan is to use exclusively open-source software for fastq to GenBank file

manipulations, and GenBank file annotations (both CLI and GUI). We do not find it

reasonable to redistribute the software as a simple indication of the name of the

software or software package and the version thereof used should suffice. Only

the impromptu "self-made" utility code for CLI will be used for day-to-day tasks.

The scale and lack of complexity of such code do not warrant its open deposition

and versioning.

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

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Notepad or Nano, among others). The availability of the comprehensive libraries

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in GenBank format programmatically. More specialized GUI software, both commercial (e.g., Geneious, etc.) and open-source (e.g., UGENE, Artemis, DNAMaster, etc.), exists for GenBank file manipulations and is largely a matter of personal preference.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

Yes

Where relevant, international standards of the field such as taxonomy ratified by the International Committee of Taxonomy of Viruses.

<https://ictv.global/taxonomy>

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Other (Public Domain)

The data will comply with the GenBank policies (GenBank® is the NIH genetic sequence database, an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences). The widest re-use will be ensured by the availability of the data without any restrictions, e.g. public domain. Citing the NCBI Molecular Data Usage (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/home/about/policies>): "Databases of molecular data on the NCBI Web site include such examples as nucleotide sequences (GenBank), protein sequences, macromolecular structures, molecular variation, gene expression, and mapping data. They are designed to provide and

encourage access within the scientific community to sources of current and comprehensive information. Therefore, NCBI itself places no restrictions on the use or distribution of the data contained therein. Nor do we accept data when the submitter has requested restrictions on reuse or redistribution."

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

No restrictions after the end of the project.

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

Indefinitely (e.g., until any of the INSDC databases -DDBJ/ENA/GenBank, still functions)

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

2.4.6 Other relevant remarks

Submissions to INSDC databases are validated by a set of automatic submission processing procedures, as well as database staff (in case of need) to meet the database standards.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

The findings will be published in open-access peer-reviewed journal with cost covered by the project funding

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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Internally curating the generated data and metadata for public release through NCBI services to INSDC databases (e.g., registering and maintaining a relevant BioProject accession, which will get populated by relevant BioSample accessions.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The project will cover the generation and processing of the data, as well as preparation of their submission to INSDC databases. After the completion project, as the respective data will be a part of the public domain, the costs associated with long-term storage and maintenance of the data will be covered externally by the INSDC databases and other relevant public biological sequence repositories.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Passwords
- Physical access control

All the data will be stored in a secure personal cloud as well as on physical storage drives for long-term storage prior to, and even after the public release through INSDC.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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